

Electrometric Studies on the Precipitation of Hydrous Oxides of Some Quadrivalent Cations. Part II. Precipitation of Thorium Hydroxide from Solutions of Thorium Salts

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Precipitation of thorium hydroxide from thorium sulphate, chloride, and nitrate solutions by sodium hydroxide shows that when equilibria are attained, the precipitates consist of basic salts having compositions $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.14}(\text{SO}_4)_{0.43}$, $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.12}\text{Cl}_{0.88}$, and $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.7}(\text{NO}_3)_{0.3}$. The anion penetration is practically of the same order in the case of sulphate and chloride, but in the case of nitrate, it is much less. Using baryta in the case of thorium sulphate solutions, it has been found that although a basic salt of about the same composition is precipitated initially, it gives up its sulphate ions on addition of more of baryta, leaving behind almost pure hydrous oxide of thorium.

In continuation of our work on the precipitation of hydrous oxides of some quadrivalent cations¹, we have now studied the precipitation of the hydrous oxides of thorium from solutions of its sulphate, chloride, and nitrate by electrometric methods. On the basis of *pH* titrations, Britton² had inferred that sodium hydroxide precipitated basic salts of the composition $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.31}(\text{SO}_4)_{0.35}$, $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.38}\text{Cl}_{0.42}$, and $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.43}(\text{NO}_3)_{0.57}$ from solutions of thorium sulphate, chloride, and nitrate respectively. These basic salts were found to suffer some decomposition further on addition of more of alkali.

The present work has been undertaken to examine the effect of the anion on the composition of the basic salts of thorium, which are precipitated by sodium hydroxide and baryta. The composition of the precipitates has been deduced from the number of equivalents of alkali consumed at various points on the titration curves. The composition of the precipitates has been found to change on keeping and equilibrium is attained within 72 hours.

EXPERIMENTAL

Pure B. D. H. samples of thorium sulphate, chloride, and nitrate were used for these investigations. Their purity was checked by gravimetric methods. 0.01*M* solutions of sulphate, chloride, and nitrate were prepared. The sulphate solutions (10 ml) were titrated against 0.392*N* solution of carbonate-free NaOH and 0.3875*N* solution of baryta. *pH* and conductometric titrations were done as described in Part I¹. The results of these titrations are summarised in the form of curves in Figs. 1-3. In the case of thorium chloride (10 ml), 0.4*N*-NaOH was used (Fig. 4), whereas in the case of nitrate, the strength of the alkali was 0.5*N* (Fig. 5).

DISCUSSION

Titration of Thorium Sulphate

The curve of continued *pH* titration (Fig. 1) shows at first a flat portion indicating gradual neutralisation of free acid obtained as a result of hydrolysis of thorium sulphate. There is then a steep rise in *pH*, the inflection appearing when 0.77 ml of alkali has been

1. This Journal, 1961, 38, 865.

2. J. Chem. Soc., 1935, 127, 2120.

added. At this stage the composition of the precipitate should have been $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.08}(\text{SO}_4)_{0.49}$. The curve for bottle titration of the same thorium sulphate solution shows that the process of hydrolysis is a slow one and in this case the inflection occurs when 0.80 ml of alkali has been added, the composition of the precipitate corresponding to $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.14}(\text{SO}_4)_{0.43}$. That this represents the equilibrium value was checked by resealing the bottles and determining the $p\text{H}$ after another interval of 48 hours.

FIG. 1. Titrations of $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_4)_2$.
O—contd.
X—bottle.

FIG. 2. Titrations of $0.0M\text{-Th}(\text{SO}_4)_2$.
O—contd.
X—bottle.

$p\text{H}$ titrations with baryta solution gave similar curves (Fig. 2), the inflections occurring at 0.79 ml of alkali in the continued and 1.02 ml of alkali in the bottle titrations. In the latter curve, an inflection at 0.80 ml is followed by a short horizontal portion and finally a second inflection at 1.02 ml. This titration was repeated with 25 ml of the thorium salt solution and the bottles were kept aside for 72 hours. The $p\text{H}$ curve (Fig. 3) has a considerably longer horizontal portion showing decomposition of the basic salt by baryta to produce thorium hydroxide and barium sulphate, both of which are insoluble. The added baryta thus being removed from the solution, the $p\text{H}$ remains constant during this stage. This aspect of the constancy of $p\text{H}$ will be discussed further in connection with the results of conductometric titrations described below. The composition of the precipitates, as deduced from the continued and bottle titration curves, would be $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.08}(\text{SO}_4)_{0.47}$ and $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{4.0}$ respectively.

Conductometric titrations were also carried out with solutions of the same strength. Continued titration with sodium hydroxide (Fig. 1) shows an initial fall in conductance

denoting the neutralisation of the strong acid present as a result of hydrolysis. The first break occurs at 0.14 ml of alkali and marks the point at which precipitation begins. The conductance then begins to rise because thorium ions are replaced by more mobile sodium ions. A second break at 0.77 ml of alkali indicates complete precipitation of the basic salt of the formula $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.02}(\text{SO}_4)_{0.49}$. This is followed by a steep rise in conductance due to the free alkali. Bottle titrations were also carried out conductometrically and a curve having similar features was obtained. The composition of the basic salt, as deduced from this curve, corresponds to the formula $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.14}(\text{SO}_4)_{0.43}$.

Conductometric titrations with baryta solution, continued and bottle (Fig. 2), show a steeper fall in conductance due to removal of H^+ and SO_4^{2-} ions from the solution. Commencement of precipitation is indicated in both cases by breaks in the curves. After the first break, the curves become less steep and then the second break occurs at 0.8 ml of alkali in the continued titration. This marks the complete precipitation of the basic salt. The rounded portion that follows shows the attack of the precipitate by the alkali. The rounded portion is followed by a steep rise due to the presence of free alkali in the solution. In the bottle titration, conductance falls to practically zero when 0.76 ml of alkali has been added and remains constant for the next 0.26 ml of baryta solution. This is followed by a steep rise in conductance due to free alkali in the solution. The constancy of conductance over a small region can be explained as follows. The precipitate consists of basic thorium sulphate and addition of baryta is responsible for its conversion into pure thorium hydroxide, barium sulphate being formed simultaneously. All these products being insoluble, conductance does not rise during this stage.

FIG. 3. Bottle titrations of $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_4)_2$.

The constancy of pH and conductance over a certain region can clearly be seen from the curves in Fig. 3 which gives the results of titrations using 25 ml of the same thorium sulphate solution instead of 10 ml as in other titrations.

The above results can also be satisfactorily explained by application of the phase rule to the system. Addition of baryta in the earlier stages causes precipitation of basic thorium sulphate according to the equation:

While the basic sulphate is precipitated, there are four phases present in the system, viz., water vapour; solution, basic thorium sulphate, and barium sulphate. The number of components is four, one of which is water, the remaining three being three of the four independent species shown in the above equation. According to the phase rule, the system can then possess two degrees of freedom. These apparently are temperature and pressure. On addition of a slight excess of baryta beyond the stage when precipitation of basic thorium sulphate is complete, a new phase, *i. e.*, pure thorium hydroxide, makes its appearance. The number of degrees of freedom is thereby reduced to unity. The temperature having been maintained constant, the only degree of freedom is lost and the system becomes non-variant as shown by the flat portions in the titration curves.

Titration of Thorium Chloride

Results of continued pH titration (Fig. 4) of thorium chloride show that at 0.74 ml of alkali, there is an inflection. In the bottle titration, the alkali consumed is slightly more, *i. e.*, 0.78 ml, the general trend of the curve remaining similar.

FIG. 4. Titrations of ThCl_4 .
1,3—contd.
2,4—bottle.

FIG. 5. Titrations of $\text{Th}(\text{NO}_3)_4$.
0—contd.
X—bottle.

The above results are confirmed by conductometric titrations, results of which are also shown by curves in Fig. 4. Each of the curves has three distinct regions corresponding to the neutralisation of the free acid, precipitation of the basic salt, and finally increase in conductance due to presence of free alkali in the solution. The small rounded portions

in the conductometric titration curves denote the partial attack of the precipitate by the alkali. The composition of the precipitates in the continued and the bottle titrations corresponds to $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{2.96}\text{Cl}_{1.04}$ and $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.12}\text{Cl}_{0.88}$ respectively as shown by both pH and conductometric titrations.

Titrations of Thorium Nitrate

Results of continued pH titrations (Fig. 5) show an inflection in the curve at 0.60 ml of alkali, which is corroborated by the continued conductometric titration curve also, shown in the figure.

In the bottle titrations, pH curve has an inflection when 0.74 ml of alkali had been added. The corresponding conductometric titration curve also has a break at 0.74 ml of alkali marking the point when precipitation of the basic salt is complete. The conductometric titration curves have the same three regions as are present in the case of the curves obtained with thorium chloride. The formulas of the basic salts obtained in the case of continued and bottle titrations, as deduced from the curves, are $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_3\text{NO}_3$ and $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.7}(\text{NO}_3)_{0.3}$ respectively.

Comparison of the titration curves of thorium chloride and nitrate with those of thorium sulphate shows that in aqueous solution, the salts are partially hydrolysed. The equilibrium is shifted by addition of alkali and the hydroxides are ultimately precipitated. The attainment of equilibrium, after addition of each portion of alkali, takes time and the precipitate in each case contains considerable amounts of the anion. In the sodium hydroxide equilibrium titrations, the composition of the precipitates corresponds to $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.14}(\text{SO}_4)_{0.43}$, $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.12}\text{Cl}_{0.88}$, and $\text{Th}(\text{OH})_{3.7}(\text{NO}_3)_{0.3}$. These results are in accord with the order of the co-ordinating power of these anions. Anion penetration in the case of sulphate and chloride, however, appears to be roughly of the same order.